

D2.3: Report on the progress of European national network engagement in RDA TIGER WGs

Project Title	Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions
Project Acronym	RDA TIGER
Grant Agreement No	101094406
Instrument	HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01
Topic	HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01-04
Start Date of Project	1 January 2023
Duration of Project	36 months
Project Website	https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-tiger

Dissemination Level

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	PU: Public
<input type="checkbox"/>	PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
<input type="checkbox"/>	CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

Work Package	WP2 - Communications
Lead Author (Org)	Genevieve Halbert (RDA Association AISBL)
Contributing Author(s) (Org)	Liise Lehtsalu, Alex Delipalta
Due Date	30 June 2025
Date	30 June 2025
Version	1.0
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.15775225

Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Authors	Notes
0.1	30.05.25	Genevieve Halbert (RDA AISBL)	Draft for internal review
0.2	13.06.25	Nina Grau (CODATA), Ryan O'Connor (RDA AISBL)	Internal review completed
1.0	30.06.25	Genevieve Halbert (RDA AISBL), Liise Lehtsalu (RDA AISBL), Alexandra Delipalta (RDA AISBL)	Final draft for submission to the EC

Disclaimer

RDA TIGER has received funding from the European Commission’s HORIZON Coordination and Support programme under the Grant Agreement no. 101094406. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

ADP	Slovenian Social Science Data Archive
AIDV	Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation
CLOCCs	Cluster Open Science Competence Centres
CNRS	French National Centre for Scientific Research
CoRDI	Conference on Research Data Infrastructures
DFHERIS	Department of Further and Higher Education, Research and Innovation and Science (Ireland)
DRI	Digital Repository of Ireland
EASST	European Association for the Study of Science and Technology
EC	European Commission
EGI	European Grid Infrastructure
EGU	European Geosciences Union
ENN	European National Network
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EUDAT	European Collaborative Data Infrastructure

FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	General Assembly
GCPA	Good Clinical Practice Alliance
GORC	Global Open Research Commons
HEA	Higher Education Authority (Ireland)
HPC	High-Performance Computing
ICDI	Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure
IDCC	International Digital Curation Conference
INFRA-EOSC	EOSC-related Horizon Europe projects
INORMS	International Network of Research Management Societies
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
LCRDM	Landelijk Coördinatiepunt Research Data Management
NOAD	National Open Access Desks
NFDI	Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur e.V.
NORF	National Open Research Forum (Ireland)
OSFair	Open Science Fair
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDM	Research Data Management
RICH	Research Infrastructures Consortium of NCP
SND	Swedish National Data Service
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable outlines the high-level plan for the RDA TIGER project to engage with European National Networks, and describes activities that have taken place at the time of writing, as well as those still being planned. The deliverable defines European National Networks, identifies key stakeholders within those networks, and outlines how national and regional RDA communities have been involved in engaging the European community with RDA TIGER-supported Working Groups, and the RDA more broadly. Finally, this document presents the next steps in continuing to engage European National Networks, both within the lifetime of the RDA TIGER project and beyond.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	5
Table of Contents	6
1. Introduction	7
2. Definition of European National Networks	8
2.1 National RDA Regions and Legacy Nodes	9
2.2 National Research Data and Infrastructure Networks	13
2.3 Open Science and Research Data Networks	14
2.4 INFRA-EOSC Projects	14
2.5 EOSC-relevant National and European Events and Initiatives	16
3. Engagement objectives	17
3.1 Promote RDA TIGER WGs to European National Networks	18
3.2 Invite Contributions from European National Networks	18
3.3 Engage European National Networks as Testers and Adopters of RDA TIGER Outputs	19
4. Engagement activities	19
4.1 Regional webinars	19
4.2 Engagement at European, Regional and National Events	20
4.3 RDA in Europe Annual Summit	21
4.4 European Newsletter	22
5. Results	23
5.1 Engaging new users and regions	23
5.2 Adoption of RDA TIGER-supported WG Outputs	24
6. Conclusion and next steps	26
Annex 1: Engagement at European, Regional and National Events	28

1. Introduction

This deliverable outlines the high-level strategy and actions undertaken by the RDA TIGER project to engage European national and regional networks in the development, implementation, and adoption of RDA TIGER-supported Research Data Alliance (RDA) Working Group (WG) Outputs, and increase their participation in the work of the RDA in general. Recognising the critical role that national stakeholders play in shaping and sustaining Europe's research data landscape, this document explores how RDA TIGER fosters deeper alignment between RDA's global mission and Europe's diverse research data ecosystems.

European National Networks (ENNs) - comprising research institutions, policy bodies, infrastructure providers, and open science advocates - form the connective tissue between European data policy ambitions and local practice. Engaging these networks is essential for ensuring that RDA WG outputs are both relevant and actionable at national levels, and that they reflect the specific needs, challenges, and priorities of diverse research communities. This level of engagement also supports the alignment of European initiatives with the broader international landscape, and ensures that regional initiatives and Europe in general remains competitive at the international level.

This deliverable begins by defining what constitutes a European National Network (ENNs) in the context of the RDA TIGER project and provides a structured overview of the various network types that have proven especially important for the project's engagement activities, from RDA Regions first and foremost to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) Federation and beyond. Furthermore, it showcases how national actors are not only contributors but also potential adopters and testbeds for emerging WG outputs.

The document then details key engagement activities deployed by the RDA TIGER project to build and sustain these connections. These include regional webinars tailored to local priorities, participation in major European events, the use of strategic communication tools such as the RDA Europe newsletter, and the launch of a new event, the RDA in Europe Summit, to enhance the engagement of the European community with RDA. Each activity serves to raise awareness of RDA TIGER WGs, invite contributions from national stakeholders, and support the adoption of WG outputs in real-world contexts.

The deliverable also addresses the growing momentum around adoption efforts, highlighting how national and regional bodies are engaging with RDA TIGER outputs through early implementation, piloting, and alignment with broader European initiatives. The forthcoming RDA in Europe Summit in November 2025 is identified as a major milestone event to consolidate this work and deepen regional integration.

Finally, the deliverable concludes with a forward-looking section outlining next steps to ensure continued and sustainable engagement with national networks, both within and beyond the lifetime of the RDA TIGER project.

2. Definition of European National Networks

European National Networks (ENNs) refer to structured communities or organisations both within individual European countries and across regional/national European boundaries that bring together stakeholders involved in Research Data Management (RDM), Open Science, and digital research infrastructure. These networks can include representatives from research institutions, universities, government agencies, industry, and other relevant entities. The engagement of European National Networks by the RDA TIGER project and by RDA TIGER-supported WGs ensures that national perspectives and challenges are addressed within the broader European research data ecosystem.

In the context of RDA TIGER, ENNs play a crucial role in:

- **Fostering collaboration:** Facilitating cooperation between national and international stakeholders in research data sharing and interoperability.
- **Promoting Open Science:** Advocating for policies and practices aligned with the Open Science approach and FAIR data principles.
- **Bridging national and international efforts:** Connecting local research communities with broader European and global research data initiatives, such as the RDA.
- **Supporting capacity building:** Providing training, best practices, and infrastructure to improve RDM within their respective countries.

ENNs identified as being particularly important to the RDA TIGER project are outlined in Table 1 and further detailed below.

Table 1: European National Networks and their relevance to the RDA TIGER project

Network	Primary Role	Unique Contribution	Strategic Importance	Examples (see dedicated sections below)
RDA national Regions and Legacy Nodes	Represent and coordinate RDA activity at the national level; maintain continuity from RDA Europe	Mobilise expert communities, support consultations, and foster WG member participation	Sustain long-term national engagement and amplify the implementation of outputs	RDA France, RDA Netherlands, RDA Slovenia, RDA Ireland

National Research Data and Infrastructure Networks	Act as key national hubs for RDM services coordination and policy implementation	Provide real-world use cases, testbed environments, and access to institutional and domain-specific infrastructures, mobilise expert communities	Enable practical testing and national-level adoption of RDA TIGER WG outputs	ICDI, NFDI, NORF, SND, LCRDM
Open Science and Research Data Networks	Promote Open Science alignment and FAIR principles across Europe	Disseminate and implement RDA TIGER-supported WG outputs, deliver training, and influence policy design	Broaden visibility and integration of RDA TIGER outputs within national and European Open Science agendas	(e.g., national Open Science forums, OpenAIRE)
INFRA-EOSC projects	EOSC-related Horizon Europe projects that aim to contribute to EOSC development and implementation	Develop cross-project synergies and cross-fertilization of outputs and results	Ensure relevance and sustainability of project outputs	FAIR-IMPACT, FAIRCORE4EOSC, EOSC-EDEN, FIDELIS
EOSC-Relevant National and European Events and Initiatives	Offer high-impact platforms for dissemination, community building, and strategic alignment	Create opportunities for cross-project collaboration and engagement with policymakers, service providers, and research communities	Position RDA TIGER within the broader EOSC ecosystem, ensuring relevance of project outputs and their alignment with European priorities	EOSC Winter Schools, EOSC Symposium, EGI Conference

2.1 National RDA Regions and Legacy Nodes

The RDA has active communities across Europe that support its mission to advance open research and education, and promote the Outputs (i.e., Recommendations, Supporting Outputs, and Other Outputs)¹ developed by RDA Groups to stakeholders throughout the region. In turn, the RDA supports European data communities in addressing their regional data-related challenges by finding solutions, fostering intra-European dialogue, and enabling connections to governing bodies such as the European Commission (EC). The RDA has several Regional Members² in Europe, with over half of its total membership being based in the region. The European Regions contribute to the RDA community's work by participating in core activities, such as plenaries, Working and Interest Groups, workshops, and the collaborative creation and adoption of Outputs. They bring the specific challenges that are unique to each European area to the RDA community and work together with global partners to find solutions to their challenges.

RDA Regions (including the RDA 'Legacy Nodes', initially established during the EC-funded RDA Europe 4.0 project³ in 2018-2020) are identified as key assets to the RDA TIGER project, and efforts have been made to further support their engagement with RDA. RDA regions serve as existing bridges between the global RDA community and national research ecosystems, and their continued engagement is essential to achieving strengthened European collaboration, RDA WG participation and Output adoption. The project has worked to engage with European RDA regions⁴ both as amplifiers for the work carried out by its supported WGs, and to support their engagement with RDA in general.

The RDA Regions in Europe with active and formal collaborations with the RDA are outlined below:

- RDA in Ireland⁵: Led by the Digital Repository of Ireland⁶, RDA Ireland focuses on connecting researchers working with research data in Ireland with the broader RDA activities. They have a particular emphasis on libraries, the social sciences, and digital humanities.
- RDA in Netherlands⁷: The Dutch RDA node, through the Dutch Research Council⁸, has been instrumental in support, adoption and implementation of CoreTrustSeal⁹, a certification for trustworthy data repositories.

¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/>

² <https://www.rd-alliance.org/membership/regional-membership/>

³ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/777388>

⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/regions-rda-europe/>

⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-ireland/activity/>

⁶ <https://dri.ie/>

⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-netherlands/activity/>

⁸ <https://www.nwo.nl/>

⁹ <https://www.coretrustseal.org/>

- RDA in France¹⁰: The CNRS¹¹ hosts the national chapter of the RDA, RDA France, initially established as part of the RDA Europe 4.0 project. The Ministry of Higher Education and Research¹² supports the operation of the RDA and RDA France, as part of the National Plan for Open Science.
- RDA in Slovenia¹³: Social Science Data Archive (ADP) at the University of Ljubljana hosts the national chapter of the RDA, RDA Slovenia, initially established as part of the RDA Europe 4.0 project. In 2025, Slovenia, through ADP, joined RDA as a regional partner to support the data-related objectives of the National Action Plan for Open Science.¹⁴
- RDA Europe¹⁵: The RDA TIGER Coordinator, RDA AISBL, is the pan-European office of the RDA, facilitating connections across and between the regions, and providing links with the global RDA. As part of our WP2 and WP3 activities within the RDA TIGER project, we have engaged existing and 'legacy' RDA regions in Europe.
- RDA in United Kingdom: UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)¹⁶ hosts the RDA UK region, the second largest regional RDA community.

It should be noted that the active European RDA membership is not limited to the regions referenced above. The images below provide further insight into the size and level of engagement with RDA in Europe for regional (image 1) and individual (image 2) membership.

¹⁰ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-france/activity/>

¹¹ <https://www.cnrs.fr/fr>

¹² <https://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/fr>

¹³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-slovenia/activity/>

¹⁴ <https://www.cessda.eu/News/CESSDA-Newsitem-nid4765>

¹⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/rda-europe-office/>

¹⁶ <https://www.ukri.org/>

Image 1. RDA Regional Membership data as of May 2025

Image 2. RDA Individual Membership data as of May 2025

2.2 National Research Data and Infrastructure Networks

These networks have been identified as stakeholders in the RDA TIGER project, serving as the primary connectors between national-level research communities and European or global initiatives like the RDA. Examples include:

- Italian Computing and Data Infrastructure (ICDI)¹⁷: A forum of major Italian research infrastructures and e-infrastructure with the aim to promote synergies at national level and coordinate Italian engagement with European and global data initiatives, including EOSC, European Data Infrastructure and HPC. ICDI also hosts the Skills4EOSC Competence Centre in Italy, which also includes the Italian Data Steward Network. RDA TIGER has engaged with the Italian Data Steward Network in particular, sharing TIGER-related events and news in the network's mailing list.
- German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI)¹⁸: a network of research performing organisations, universities, libraries, learned societies and associations that aims to develop the framework for legally compliant, interoperable and sustainable data infrastructure in Germany. NFDI members form disciplinary or cross-cutting consortia that develop services to achieve the vision of NFDI. RDA TIGER engages with a number of NFDI consortia and working groups as they are stakeholders in RDA TIGER supported WGs; RDA TIGER also engages with Base4NFDI on facilitation services, comparing how services are set up and delivered.
- National Open Research Forum (NORF)¹⁹ Ireland: NORF provides a space for communication, consultation and cooperation among key stakeholders in the research system regarding strategic issues and overarching policies and procedures in open research. The Forum combines the expertise of representatives from policy, research funding organisations, research performing organisations, the library sector, enterprise and other key stakeholders in the research system across Ireland. It is funded by the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research and Innovation and Science (DFHERIS)²⁰ through the Higher Education Authority (HEA)²¹. It is managed by the Digital Repository of Ireland (DRI)²².

Additional Network examples for future engagement:

- Swedish National Data Service (SND)²³: a national research infrastructure that supports making all types of digital research data accessible by providing a national research data portal, PID services, and metadata services.

¹⁷ <https://www.icdi.it/it/>

¹⁸ <https://www.nfdi.de/>

¹⁹ <https://dri.ie/norf/>

²⁰ <https://gov.ie/en/department-of-further-and-higher-education-research-innovation-and-science/>

²¹ <https://hea.ie/>

²² <https://dri.ie/>

²³ <https://snd.se/en>

- National Coordination Point Research Data Management (LCRDM)²⁴: a national network of experts in the field of research data management (RDM) in the Netherlands.

2.3 Open Science and Research Data Networks

Across Europe, and beyond, networks promote Open Science, FAIR principles and research data management practices by developing and coordinating support services, training, and good practice. These networks play a strategic role in the success and impact of the RDA TIGER project by increasing visibility and adoption-potential of RDA TIGER and RDA WG outputs. RDA TIGER has referred to these networks to identify target audiences for dissemination and communication activities and target users for project and RDA outputs. Examples include:

- GO FAIR National Offices²⁵: Many European countries have GO FAIR nodes, such as GO FAIR France and GO FAIR Germany, which work to implement FAIR data principles.
- Europe-based Reproducibility Networks²⁶: National networks focused on improving research reproducibility and open research practices.
- OpenAIRE National Open Access Desks (NOADs)²⁷: Each European country has an OpenAIRE NOAD that helps researchers comply with Open Science policies and fosters national engagement.
- Skills4EOSC Competence Centres Network²⁸: A coordinated network of Competence Centres across Europe that provides key competencies to enable the practice of Open Science and EOSC.
- Cluster Open Science Competence Centres (CLOCCs)²⁹: An OSCARS Project initiative to create hubs dedicated to fostering research excellence through training and knowledge transfer.

2.4 INFRA-EOSC Projects

INFRA-EOSC Horizon Europe projects contribute to the development and implementation of EOSC. RDA TIGER, which is a INFRA-EOSC project, engages with other INFRA-EOSC projects to develop synergies between projects and support the uptake and sustainability of project outputs within the EOSC ecosystem. Examples include:

- FAIR-IMPACT³⁰ and FAIRCORE4EOSC³¹ projects: These sister projects developed new EOSC core components (FAIRCORE4EOSC) and supported the adoption of FAIR

²⁴ <https://lcrdm.nl/>

²⁵ <https://www.go-fair.org/national-offices/>

²⁶ <https://www.ukrn.org/global-networks/>

²⁷ <https://www.openaire.eu/contact-noads>

²⁸ <https://www.skills4eosc.eu/network>

²⁹ <https://oscars-project.eu/clusters-open-science-competence-centres>

³⁰ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101057344>

³¹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101057264>

principles in the EOSC ecosystem (FAIR-IMPACT). RDA TIGER facilitates the RDA FAIR Mappings WG that builds on mappings registry³² and mappings recommendations³³ developed in FAIRCORE4EOSC and FAIR-IMPACT, thus supporting the uptake and sustainability of those outputs.

- OSTRails³⁴ project: RDA TIGER facilitates the RDA maDMPs WG³⁵ that builds on and supports the work OSTRails has set out to do around extending the RDA maDMP Common Model³⁶.
- EOSC EDEN³⁷ and EOSC FIDELIS³⁸ projects: These sister projects, both coordinated by CSC in Finland, aim to advance digital preservation and curation in Europe. Two RDA TIGER facilitated RDA WGs (RDA TRUST WG³⁹ and RDA TRSPs WG⁴⁰) develop outputs of direct relevance to EOSC EDEN and EOSC FIDELIS. RDA TIGER supports cross-fertilisation between EDEN-FIDELIS and the two WGs; a joint public webinar is expected in autumn 2025.
- EOSC Data Commons⁴¹: The EOSC Data Commons project works to establish the European Open Science Cloud as a trusted European Research Commons, fostering seamless access to high-quality, interoperable research outputs and services. The project to implement the Output of the GORC International Model WG (an RDA TIGER-supported WG) across EOSC⁴².

³² Kesäniemi, J. (2024, May 14). MSCR - Metadata Schema and Crosswalk Registry. SYMPOSIUM "CROSS-CUTTING RESEARCH SUPPORT SERVICES", Vienna, Austria. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11192310>

³³ Le Franc, Y., GRAU, N., Juty, N., Mejias, G., Reed, P., Ramezani, P., Poveda-Villalon, M., Garijo, D., Goble, C., & van Horik, R. (2025). D4.5 - Guidelines and methodology to create, document and share mappings and crosswalks (V1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111167>

³⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101130187>

³⁵

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/common-application-programming-interface-api-for-machine-actionable-data-management-plans-madmps/activity/>

³⁶ <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00039>

³⁷ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101188015>

³⁸ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101188078>

³⁹

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rdawds-trust-principles-outreach-and-adoption-working-group/activity/>

⁴⁰

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/community-based-catalogue-requirements-trustworthy-technical-repository-service-providers/activity/>

⁴¹ <https://www.eosc-data-commons.eu/>

⁴² RDA TIGER recognises the widespread use and high value of the GORC International Model in Europe; as a result, two new related WGs are also supported by RDA TIGER (with GORC International Implementations WG –

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/gorc-international-implementations-working-group-gorc-ii-wg/activity/> – and Health Data Commons GORC WG –

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/health-data-commons-gorc-profile-wg/activity/>).

2.5 EOSC-relevant National and European Events and Initiatives

These events and initiatives represent touchpoints through which RDA TIGER has amplified project visibility, reinforced the value of project outputs, and deepened engagement with national and European stakeholders, including research communities, service providers, research infrastructures, policy makers, and EOSC. These events and initiatives have helped to position RDA TIGER within the broader EOSC ecosystem, ensuring relevance of project outputs and their alignment with national, European and EOSC priorities. Key examples are provided below, with a comprehensive list available in Annex 1: Engagement at European, Regional and National Events:

- **EOSC Winter Schools:** The EOSC Winter Schools in 2024⁴³ and in 2025⁴⁴ are an initiative by the EOSC Association, with the support of the EOSC Focus project⁴⁵, to foster collaboration among Horizon Europe EOSC-related projects. The RDA TIGER team, which also includes EOSC Opportunity Area⁴⁶ and Task Force Members⁴⁷, attended both Winter Schools and leveraged this forum to engage the wider EOSC community with RDA TIGER activities and results.
- **EOSC Symposiums:** The EOSC Symposium 2023⁴⁸ and 2024⁴⁹ presented an opportunity to highlight RDA TIGER's contribution to key EOSC stakeholders (research communities, research infrastructures, service providers, research organisations, and policy makers), other EOSC-related projects and the EOSC Association. The focus of RDA TIGER engagement was twofold; highlighting RDA TIGER alignment with EOSC priorities such as interoperability, policy alignment, and user uptake of services and outputs, and encouraging the internationalisation of EC-funded project results using the RDA as a forum and leveraging the RDA TIGER support services.
- **EOSC Association General Assemblies (GAs):** The RDA TIGER consortium members are highly engaged with the EOSC ecosystem, some of them also as Members of the EOSC Association. Participation in the EOSC GAs has been an additional, though indirect, way for the RDA TIGER consortium to contribute to the EOSC activities and gain insights into areas where the work of the RDA and its WGs can complement and enrich the work of the EOSC community.
- **EGI Conferences**⁵⁰: These conferences bring together researchers, infrastructure providers, and EOSC stakeholders to discuss federated cloud, compute, and data services. They offer a platform to present WG outputs, align with EOSC service integration strategies, and engage infrastructure operators at

⁴³ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/winter-school-2024/>

⁴⁴ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/winter-school-2025/>

⁴⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058432>

⁴⁶ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-opportunity-area-expert-groups/>

⁴⁷ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-association/eosc-task-forces/>

⁴⁸ <https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/>

⁴⁹ <https://eosc.eu/symposium2024/eosc-symposium-2024-outcomes-and-resources/>

⁵⁰ <https://www.egi.eu/egi-conference/>

national and European levels. RDA TIGER was present at EGI2024 and EGI2025 conferences, contributing to an ‘interoperability booth’ together with FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC in 2024 and presenting two key RDA TIGER outputs (RDA Knowledge Base and the landscape analysis on the value of RDA outputs to the EOSC ecosystem) in 2025.

- **EUDAT Conference**⁵¹: This conference brings together data infrastructure providers, research communities, and policymakers from across Europe. RDA TIGER participated at the EUDAT Conference 2024 with an exhibition booth and a poster presenting RDA TIGER outputs with a particular focus on the RDA Knowledge Base. Engagement at EUDAT strengthened relationships with service providers and promoted adoption of RDA TIGER outputs by national infrastructures, ensuring their alignment with evolving EOSC priorities.
- **International Digital Curation Conference (IDCC)**⁵²: These conferences bring together global data curation, data preservation and RDM professionals, and have a very strong European participation. RDA TIGER contributed to IDCC in 2024 and in 2025, showcasing RDA TIGER services through posters and a talk and engaging with participants through a RDA TIGER booth that facilitated in-depth conversations about RDA TIGER activities and outputs with current and potential stakeholders and adopters.
- **LIBER Annual Conference**⁵³: This is a key annual conference for research librarians and information professionals in Europe. RDA TIGER engaged with the LIBER community at the Annual Conference in 2025 via posters and a workshop co-organised together with the LIBER Data Science in Libraries Working Group. The conference allowed RDA TIGER to introduce relevant RDA WG outputs to the library community and identify shared interests between the RDA and the LIBER community to build on RDA TIGER outputs in the future.
- **Open Science FAIR (OSFair)**⁵⁴: OSFair brings together Open Science communities and services to learn from one another and to identify synergies. RDA TIGER promotes project outputs and results at OSFair 2025. The aim is to demonstrate the relevance of RDA TIGER outputs and results to Open Science implementation across diverse national contexts, to identify national, regional and European adoption cases, and to support further alignment of RDA TIGER’s outputs with other European Open Science initiatives.

3. Engagement objectives

The engagement of ENNs is a cornerstone of the RDA TIGER project’s strategy to foster a more integrated and FAIR-aligned research data ecosystem across Europe in support of the

⁵¹ <https://eudat.eu/events/conferences>

⁵² <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/events/idcc>

⁵³ <https://libereurope.eu/annual-conference-page/>

⁵⁴ <https://www.opensciencefair.eu/>

development of the EOSC. This section outlines the key objectives that underpin the project's efforts to involve European and national networks in the development, dissemination, and implementation of RDA TIGER WGs and their outputs and with RDA in general .

3.1 Promote RDA TIGER WGs to European National Networks

The first engagement objective is to ensure broad awareness of the RDA TIGER services and RDA TIGER-supported WGs among EENs. RDA-TIGER supported WGs address critical challenges in a range of research data related topics and aim to produce practical, consensus-based RDA-endorsed Outputs that reflect both global standards and European priorities. Promoting RDA TIGER services and RDA TIGER-supported WGs across European and national contexts serves to:

- Encourage the alignment of European and national priorities with international Open Science and FAIR data practices;
- Bridge the gap between high-level policy and on-the-ground implementation;
- Amplify the relevance and visibility of RDA WGs to European and national research communities;
- Encourage contribution to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Through targeted communication, national outreach events, and strategic use of European and regional channels , RDA TIGER raises awareness and encourages participation in RDA WG activities to reach the objective above.

3.2 Invite Contributions from European National Networks

The second engagement objective is to create opportunities for meaningful contributions from European and national networks to the work of the RDA TIGER-supported WGs. This includes:

- Encouraging individuals to become new RDA members and join relevant RDA TIGER-supported WGs;
- Inviting individuals and organisations to participate in and contribute to consultations, workshops, and WG meetings;
- Invite individuals and organisations to contribute expertise and co-develop WG outputs that reflect the diversity of European and national research practices.

Involving European and national actors in RDA TIGER-supported WGs ensures the WG outputs are grounded in and applicable to local contexts, increasing the likelihood of their adoption in national and European (e.g. EOSC) settings and their long-term impact.

3.3 Engage European National Networks as Testers and Adopters of RDA TIGER Outputs

The third engagement objective is to actively involve European and national networks in piloting and adopting RDA and RDA TIGER outputs (see also Table 3 in section 5.2 below for further detail). These networks are uniquely positioned to evaluate how outputs perform across different disciplines, institutional contexts, and national infrastructures. Moreover, these networks include individuals and organisations that serve as adopters of RDA and RDA TIGER outputs. This third engagement objective includes:

- Gathering real-world feedback to refine RDA TIGER-supported WG recommendations and outputs; .
- Fostering early buy-in from key stakeholders, which supports sustained dissemination and exploitation WG recommendations and outputs;
- Demonstrating the feasibility and scalability of outputs across the European Research Area;
- Supporting interoperability in the European Open Science Cloud.

Through this hands-on engagement, RDA TIGER not only tests the practical value of its outputs but also builds capacity and trust among European research communities.

4. Engagement activities

To engage European National Networks, the RDA TIGER project has implemented a range of targeted engagement activities designed to connect European, regional and national stakeholders with the RDA TIGER services, RDA TIGER-supported WGs, their activities and outputs. These activities are outlined below.

4.1 Regional webinars

As part of RDA TIGER's efforts to strengthen ties with regional and national stakeholders, a series of webinars targeting RDA regions in Europe was organised in 2024 and 2025. These webinars provided a focused platform to introduce the RDA and the RDA TIGER-supported WGs to specific national communities, highlight locally relevant engagement pathways, and showcase contributions from regional data professionals. By aligning RDA messaging with national priorities and creating space for dialogue, these webinars played a vital role in fostering awareness, encouraging participation, and building momentum for the adoption of RDA TIGER activities across Europe.

Table 2: Webinars targeting RDA Regions in Europe

Region	Date	Format	Engagement Relevance to RDA TIGER
Slovenia	28 November 2024	Online	Co-hosted with RDA Slovenia; focused on the state of Open Science and data infrastructure in Slovenia. Showcased national initiatives and introduced RDA and TIGER WGs as channels for contributing to broader EU research data goals.
Baltics	26 March 2025	Online	Introduced RDA to research data professionals in Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania. Highlighted benefits of engagement, spotlighted relevant WGs (e.g. FAIR for ML IG), and profiled national contributors, helping connect Baltic networks to RDA TIGER. ⁵⁵
Poland	4 June 2025	Online	Introduced selected RDA and RDA TIGER groups to Polish data professionals with the aim to highlight where and how these professionals can get involved. ⁵⁶
Ireland	26 September 2025 (TBC)	Online	Will highlight RDA and RDA TIGER activity that is of particular relevance to Ireland, including national priorities and infrastructure developments. Will be a platform for explaining how Irish institutions can participate in and benefit from TIGER WG outputs, and inviting stakeholder involvement in ongoing WG activities.
Denmark	TBC	Online	May focus on Danish data policy priorities and existing engagement with RDA, including promotion of TIGER WGs relevant to Denmark's data stewardship and FAIR implementation landscape. May be an opportunity to encourage input and future collaboration from national research infrastructures.

4.2 Engagement at European, Regional and National Events

⁵⁵ Lehtsalu, L. (2025, March 26). RDA in the Baltics. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15088984>

⁵⁶ Lehtsalu, L. (2025, June 30). RDA and the Polish Data Community. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15773023>

Attendance at European, regional and national events offers a strategic opportunity for the RDA TIGER project to connect with a broad spectrum of national, regional and European stakeholders in the research data and Open Science ecosystem. In particular, engagement at these events targeted four key networks identified in Section 2: National Research Data and Infrastructure Networks, Open Science and Research Data Networks, INFRA-EOSC Projects and EOSC-relevant National and European Events and Initiatives. These events serve as high-visibility platforms to promote RDA TIGER services and RDA TIGER-supported WGs, showcase activities, progress and outputs, and invite participation from and adoption by communities that may not be directly involved in RDA structures. By presenting at conferences, workshops, and symposia with strong national representation, the project can build relationships, raise awareness of WG activities, and encourage uptake and testing of WG outputs by institutions and infrastructures across Europe.

The full list of RDA TIGER engagement at European, regional and national events is included in Annex 1.

4.3 RDA in Europe Annual Summit

In November 2025, RDA Europe and RDA France will collaborate to stage the inaugural RDA in Europe Annual Summit⁵⁷. The European RDA membership is invited to gather, along with key stakeholders from across Europe, to address specific regional challenges, priorities, and opportunities in research data management and Open Science.

The event will provide a dedicated forum for current and prospective European RDA regions and their members to address challenges and solutions at both national and pan-European levels, and discuss RDA's role and priorities within the broader European landscape. It will also offer an opportunity to address key topics relevant to the European RDA community, through the lens of the RDA and to advance its impact across Europe. The inaugural Summit will feature the theme of 'Weaving the RDA Tapestry: From Community Insights to Collective Action'. It will deliver a rich programme shaped by RDA European community contributions in the form of lightning talks and posters, as well as a regional roundtable with topics for discussion selected in collaboration with the European RDA regional representatives.

This summit represents a milestone opportunity to consolidate RDA TIGER's work, scale engagement across national and regional structures, and ensure its outputs are visible, valued, and sustained in the evolving European Open Science ecosystem. Some of the ways in which this will be achieved are outlined below.

- **Promotion of RDA TIGER-supported WGs to a targeted European audience:** The summit will provide an opportunity to present WG progress and priorities in sessions aligned with European data challenges and policy frameworks. This will encourage

⁵⁷ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/event/rda-europe-annual-summit/>

RDA TIGER "Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions" is funded by HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-0 Project: 101094406.

national and regional participation in WGs by showcasing tangible opportunities for national involvement.

- **Activation of national networks as contributors and collaborators:** The RDA TIGER team will facilitate regional roundtable discussions or workshops involving national research infrastructures and Open Science networks and will invite representatives from national networks to respond to WG outputs, propose new directions, or share feedback on national applicability.
- **Support for output testing and adoption:** The summit will be a platform to put out a call for adopters of RDA TIGER-supported WG outputs, targeting institutions or infrastructures from national networks. It will also be a platform for highlighting early adoption stories from within Europe to inspire further uptake. There may also be scope for hands-on workshops for interested parties to explore practical use of RDA TIGER WG outputs or recommendations.
- **Strengthening relationships with RDA regions and legacy nodes:** There will be potential for hosting a closed session for RDA national nodes and regional coordinators, with a focus on strengthening their role in RDA TIGER activities and future WG development. Sustainability of engagement beyond the RDA TIGER project would be a key topic, as well as how the summit might be a stepping-stone for renewed national coordination.
- **Positioning RDA TIGER within the broader European data landscape:** The summit will highlight how RDA TIGER aligned with EU priorities throughout its lifetime, such as EOSC and national data strategies. It will also aim to partner with EOSC-related initiatives (e.g. EOSC FIDELIS, EOSC EDEN) to show cross-project alignment.
- **Disseminate RDA TIGER outcomes:** As the final large-scale event in the project's lifetime, the RDA in Europe Annual Summit will be an opportunity to showcase the project's impact in Europe more broadly and the EOSC ecosystem in particular.

4.4 European Newsletter

The RDA Europe newsletter, sent quarterly, serves as a strategic communications and engagement tool. It helps bridge the gap between pan-European RDA efforts and national and regional stakeholders. It enhances visibility, participation, and adoption of RDA TIGER-supported WG activities and outputs by creating sustained touchpoints across Europe. Some of the ways in which the newsletter contributes to European national and regional network engagement in RDA TIGER WGs are outlined below.

- **Raising awareness of RDA TIGER WGs:** Each issue can feature relevant updates on ongoing WGs, newly launched groups, or outputs in development, ensuring national and regional stakeholders are kept informed and connected to the latest activities in a specifically European context. By presenting these updates in a clear, engaging format, the newsletter helps demystify WG processes and encourages broader participation, especially from those less directly involved in RDA structures.

- **Encouraging participation and contributions:** Calls for participation, consultations, or testing opportunities can be embedded in the newsletter, guiding stakeholders on how to engage with specific WGs. Highlighting easy entry points, such as surveys, public webinars, or case study calls, lowers the barrier for institutions and individuals to get involved.
- **Showcasing regional and national impact:** By including articles, opinion pieces, or spotlights from WG co-chairs and national contributors, the newsletter highlights how RDA TIGER WGs are relevant to real-world challenges and infrastructures. By showcasing how their peers are contributing to and benefiting from engagement with RDA TIGER WGs, the newsletter reinforces the value of engagement to national stakeholders.
- **Supporting knowledge sharing and dialogue:** The newsletter can include thematic opinion pieces on topics of strategic interest to Europe (e.g. FAIR data, interoperability, EOSC alignment), linked to relevant RDA TIGER WG work. These articles foster a sense of shared purpose, stimulate discussion, and position RDA as a thought leader on European data policy and practice.
- **Strengthening a cohesive European RDA community:** Regular updates and region-specific content help cultivate a distinct European identity within RDA, where national networks feel part of a unified, evolving effort. It gives visibility to the work of different RDA regions and legacy nodes, encouraging interconnection and collaboration.
- **Facilitating Strategic Alignment:** The newsletter can highlight how RDA TIGER WG outputs relate to European data initiatives (e.g. EOSC, NFDI, OpenAIRE), helping national actors understand the strategic relevance of their participation. This alignment messaging strengthens the policy and funding case for national stakeholders to engage and invest in RDA TIGER-aligned efforts.

5. Results

5.1 Engaging new users and regions

New RDA Regions

The project team's engagement with the regional communities of RDA has contributed to the development of two new RDA Regions during the project lifetime:

- RDA in Slovenia was formalised as a Partner Region in late 2024;
- RDA in Belgium became an 'interested' Region in May 2024, with representatives of the local RDA community joining the Regional Assembly.

Presentation of RDA TIGER at events

A KPI for the project tracks presentation of RDA TIGER in third party events during the project lifetime (not limited to national and/or European events). Events offer key opportunities to raise the visibility of RDA TIGER services and WGs, highlight their progress and outputs, and engage

new audiences beyond the core RDA community. By participating in conferences, workshops, and symposia with significant national representation, the project has strengthened connections with ENNS, increased awareness of WG activities, and promoted the adoption and testing of outputs by institutions and infrastructures across Europe (see Annex 1: Engagement at European, Regional and National Events for an overview of the events at which RDA TIGER has engaged).

Participant attendance at RDA TIGER regional webinars

Attendance at RDA Europe’s regional webinars has been good, and the webinars have received high engagement and positive feedback. See below for the attendance statistics:

- RDA in Slovenia, 28 Nov 2024: 20 participants
- RDA in the Baltics, 26 Mar 2025: 37 participants
- RDA in Poland, 4 June 2025: 90 participants

Limitations

The RDA website has been undergoing a change of provider and platform since 2023. As a result there has been significant disruption of normal back-end processes throughout the RDA TIGER project lifetime, which has made it challenging for the WP2 team to accurately track a number of related WP2 KPIs, including new individual members.

5.2 Adoption of RDA TIGER-supported WG Outputs

The adoption of RDA TIGER-supported WG outputs by regional and national service providers plays a critical role in deepening engagement with European National Networks. When service providers (such as national data infrastructures, repositories, and Open Science platforms) integrate TIGER outputs into their practices, they demonstrate the practical value and relevance of RDA’s work within national contexts. This validates the applicability of WG recommendations and encourages further participation from local stakeholders, who see tangible benefits from involvement. Adoption also helps build momentum, fosters trust, and creates a feedback loop where national experiences can shape future WG activities, strengthening the alignment between European needs and global research data solutions. Examples of RDA TIGER-supported WG outputs adopted by regional/national service providers are listed in the table below.

Table 3: Adoption of RDA TIGER-supported WG outputs

RDA TIGER-supported WGs ⁵⁸	Output	Adopter	Region
The Global Open Research Commons (GORC) International Model WG ⁵⁹	The GORC International Model ⁶⁰	REASON (ResEARch CommonS for Norway)	Norway
The Global Open Research Commons (GORC) International Model WG	The GORC International Model	SURF Data Repository	Netherlands
National PID Strategies WG ⁶¹	RDA National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist ⁶²	Digital Repository of Ireland ⁶³	Ireland
EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation Working Group (AIDV-WG) ⁶⁴	AI Bills of Rights Recommendation ⁶⁵	Good Clinical Practice Alliance (GCPA) ⁶⁶	Europe
EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation	Secure Processing Environments for Open Science: Proposing Legal	Good Clinical Practice Alliance (GCPA)	Europe

⁵⁸ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/>

⁵⁹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/gorc-international-model-wg/activity/>

⁶⁰ Woodford, C. J., Treloar, A., Leggott, M., Payne, K., Jones, S., Lopez Albacete, J., Madalli, D., Genova, F., Dharmawardena, K., Chibhira, N., Nyberg Åkerström, W., MacNeil, R., Nurnberger, A., Pfeiffenberger, H., Tanifuji, M., Zhang, Q., Jones, N., Sesink, L., & Wood-Charlson, E. (2024). *The Global Open Research Commons International Model, Version 1.1* (Version 1.1). Research Data Alliance. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00119>

⁶¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/national-pid-strategies-wg/activity/>

⁶² Simons, N., Brown, C., Bangert, D., & Sadler, S. (2023). *National PID Strategies Guide and Checklist* (Version 1.0). Research Data Alliance. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA/00091>

⁶³ <https://dri.ie/>

⁶⁴ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/artificial-intelligence-and-data-visitation-aidv-wg/activity/>

⁶⁵ Ezigbo, E., Martis B, S., Meyers, N., Purian, R., Su, Y., & RDA Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation (AIDV) WG. (2024). *AI Bill of Rights Recommendation* (Version 2.3). Research Data Alliance. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00123>

⁶⁶ <https://gcpalliance.org/about/>

Working Group (AIDV-WG)	Foundations ⁶⁷		
EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation Working Group (AIDV-WG)	Guidance for Ethics Committees Reviewing AI and DV ⁶⁸	Good Clinical Practice Alliance (GCPA)	Europe
EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation Working Group (AIDV-WG)	Guidance for Informed Consent in the context of Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation ⁶⁹	Good Clinical Practice Alliance (GCPA)	Europe

6. Conclusion and next steps

The engagement of ENNs has proven vital to advancing the RDA TIGER project's mission: to drive forward a coordinated, inclusive, and impact-oriented research data ecosystem across Europe. Through a combination of targeted outreach, regionally tailored webinars, strategic event participation, and regular communication via the RDA Europe newsletter, the project has succeeded in establishing meaningful connections between the RDA TIGER-supported WGs and the diverse array of stakeholders that shape research data policy and practice across the continent.

These engagement efforts have demonstrated the value of grounding global RDA activities in national and regional contexts. National research data infrastructures, Open Science advocates, EOSC-aligned initiatives, and long-standing RDA nodes have all contributed to shaping, testing, and amplifying the outputs of RDA TIGER-supported WGs. In turn, RDA TIGER has offered these communities a platform for visibility, influence, and integration into broader European data strategies.

Looking ahead, the next phase of engagement will prioritise:

⁶⁷ Bernier, A., Okengwu, U., & RDA Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation WG. (2025). Secure Processing Environments for Open Science: Proposing Legal Foundations (Version 1). Research Data Alliance. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00129>

⁶⁸ Pahlevan-Ibrekic, C., Sokolchik, V., Sitorus, R., Elif Ekmekci, P., Razuvanau, A., Kaplan, Ü., Prawiroharjo, P., & RDa Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation WG. (2025). Guidance for Ethics Committees Reviewing AI and DV. Research Data Alliance. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00122>

⁶⁹ Jacob Retanan, L., Dubruel, N., Chassang, G., Hackett, K., Cambon-Thomsen, A., & RDA Artificial Intelligence Data Visitation Working Group (AIDV WG). (2024). Guidance for Informed Consent in the Context of Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation (Version 2). Research Data Alliance. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00121>

- Deepening WG adoption pathways: Supporting national and regional service providers in piloting, adapting, and embedding RDA TIGER-supported WG outputs in real-world contexts.
- Activating national networks as sustained contributors: Empowering national nodes and Open Science communities to continue shaping WG activities and carrying forward their outcomes beyond the project's lifetime.
- Scaling success stories: Documenting and disseminating examples of national engagement and adoption to inspire further uptake and encourage policy alignment.
- Building durable European structures: Using the RDA in Europe Annual Summit and other flagship events to cement a coordinated and collaborative framework for RDA activities across Europe.
- Aligning with European priorities: Continuing to position RDA TIGER within the evolving landscape of EOSC, FAIR data initiatives, and national digital strategies, ensuring that WG outputs remain relevant, visible, and strategically aligned.

As the project moves toward its final stages, these next steps will be instrumental in ensuring the long-term sustainability of TIGER's impact, reinforcing the role of RDA as a key enabler of European research data collaboration, and ensuring that the momentum built through national engagement translates into meaningful and lasting change across the research ecosystem.

Annex 1: Engagement at European, Regional and National Events

Event	Date	Location	Relevance to RDA TIGER Engagement	Level of engagement
EOSC Winter School⁷⁰	January 2023; January 2025	Thessaloniki, Greece; Seville, Spain	Provision of training and policy alignment context. Opportunity to raise awareness of TIGER WGs among EOSC-related projects and national stakeholders.	European
OSFair	September 2023; September 2025	Madrid, Spain; Geneva, Switzerland	<p>At OSFair 2023, RDA TIGER presented a poster introducing the conference attendees to RDA and outlining the broad disciplinary and geographic domains covered by RDA TIGER-supported WGs.⁷¹</p> <p>In 2025, the RDA TIGER team will present a demo on the RDA Knowledge Base.</p> <p>Furthermore, in coordination with the RDA TIGER-supported AIDV WG a</p>	European

⁷⁰ <https://eosc.eu/events/eosc-winter-school-2025/>

⁷¹ O'Connor, R., Asmi, A., & Rettberg, N. (2023). *Bringing Open Science to Life: How RDA Supports Data Sharing*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8397924>

Event	Date	Location	Relevance to RDA TIGER Engagement	Level of engagement
			panel will be held on the topic of 'Data for AI: From Readiness to Ethics'.	
EOSC Symposia	September 2023; October 2024	Madrid, Spain; Berlin, Germany	The EOSC Symposium 2023 ⁷² and 2024 ⁷³ presented an opportunity to highlight RDA TIGER's contribution to key EOSC stakeholders (research communities, research infrastructures, service providers, research organisations, and policy makers), other EOSC-related projects and the EOSC Association. The focus of RDA TIGER engagement was twofold; highlighting RDA TIGER alignment with EOSC priorities such as interoperability, policy alignment, and user uptake of services and outputs, and encouraging the internationalisation of EC-funded project results using the RDA as a forum and leveraging the RDA TIGER support services.	European

⁷² <https://symposium23.eoscfuture.eu/>

⁷³ <https://eosc.eu/symposium2024/eosc-symposium-2024-outcomes-and-resources/>

Event	Date	Location	Relevance to RDA TIGER Engagement	Level of engagement
IDCC (International Digital Curation Conference)⁷⁴	February 2024; February 2025	Edinburgh, UK The Hague, the Netherlands	Networking with data stewardship professionals and national infrastructure actors. Opportunity to share TIGER WG updates and seek feedback. At the 2025, RDA TIGER Facilitation Service presented as a best practice. ⁷⁵	International, European
National EOSC Tripartite Event Brussels (2024)⁷⁶	April 2024	Brussels, Belgium	Aiming to further engage European national networks, RDA TIGER attended this meeting, which resulted in the addition of Belgium to the 'interested' RDA Regions, and the inclusion of Belgian representatives to the RDA Regional Assembly.	National
RICH Europe's first Symposium of Research Infrastructures	7 May 2024	Madrid, Spain	RDA TIGER, among other relevant EOSC projects, presented the work of the project and its supported WGs, highlighting the RDA's value for Research Infrastructures.	European

⁷⁴ <https://eosc.eu/events/19th-international-digital-curation-conference/>

⁷⁵ Lehtsalu, L., Papadopoulou, A., & O'Connor, R. (2025, March 4). RDA TIGER: Soft Infrastructure to Facilitate Community-Driven Standards for Research Data Management. 19th International Digital Curation Conference (IDCC25), The Hague, Netherlands. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14965049>

⁷⁶ <https://eosc.eu/news/2024/04/national-tripartite-event-belgium/>

Event	Date	Location	Relevance to RDA TIGER Engagement	Level of engagement
Knowledge hub live event of the Flemish Data Stewards community⁷⁷	June 2024	Brussels, Belgium	RDA TIGER project members were invited to present insights from the RDA community and processes. RDA was invited to present on stakeholder involvement, cross-collaboration, decision-making processes, and success stories or use cases that could inspire this community of data stewards & RDM support staff in Flanders.	National
Research Infrastructures conference⁷⁸ and e-IRG workshop⁷⁹	June 2024	Brussels, Belgium	In the context of engaging the range of RDA stakeholders identified as key within RDA TIGER, the project attended this conference and co-located workshop focused on "e-Infrastructure activities in the new European Research Area (ERA), which included discussions on Artificial Intelligence, Cybersecurity, and EU Data Spaces in relation to Research Infrastructures, also highlighting the role of e-Infrastructures in this area, spanning several layers and components, with a cross-cutting one being the EOSC and	National, European

⁷⁷ <https://www.frdn.be/>

⁷⁸ https://www.belspo.be/belspo/EUBelgium24/2024060405_ResearchInfrastructures_en.stm

⁷⁹ https://www.belspo.be/belspo/EUBelgium24/20240605_e-IRG_en.stm

Event	Date	Location	Relevance to RDA TIGER Engagement	Level of engagement
			thematic (domain-specific) or generic (domain-agnostic) data infrastructures.	
Sonraí Conference, Ireland⁸⁰	June 2024	Cork, Ireland	The Project connected with the local Open Science community with a focus on Data Stewardship in Ireland. The event was a first step towards engaging Ireland with the project's activities, leading to cascade grant applications supporting further the connection of the local networks with the EOSC ecosystem.	National
European Association for the Study of Science and Technology (EASST)	July 2024	Amsterdam, The Netherlands	RDA Europe was invited to a panel discussion focusing on highlighting community-centred perspectives of Research Infrastructures and exploring unexpected modes of knowledge production and co-creation opportunities. During the session, the RDA TIGER project was presented and acknowledged for its significant contribution in supporting the RDA community. Its portfolio of services and tools was recognised as invaluable in facilitating Working Group activities and	European / International

⁸⁰ <https://datastewards.ie/conference/>

Event	Date	Location	Relevance to RDA TIGER Engagement	Level of engagement
			advancing the development of impactful outputs and recommendations.	
Barcelona Declaration Principles Conference	September 2024	Paris, France	RDA Europe was invited as a new supporter of the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information. The relevance to RDA TIGER was to do with the overlapping concerns of the topics of the conference (e.g., community building, infrastructure sustainability, etc) and issues facing RDA TIGER-supported WGs.	European/International
EGI Conference 2024 (Joint RDA TIGER, FAIR IMPACT, FAIRCORE4EOSC presence)⁸¹	October 2024	Lecce, Italy	Presentation of RDA TIGER's work in relation to interoperability and its contribution to the EOSC partnership. Joint flyer with FAIR-IMPACT and FAIRCORE4EOSC.	European
RDA in Netherlands regional event	November 2024	Utrecht	RDA Europe was invited to present during this regional RDA community gathering. The presentation included an overview of regionally-relevant Outputs, and available support opportunities through RDA TIGER.	National

⁸¹ <https://www.egi.eu/article/meet-egi2024-exhibitors-fair-impact-rda-tiger-faircore4eosc/>

Event	Date	Location	Relevance to RDA TIGER Engagement	Level of engagement
Arnes annual Network of Knowledge Conference, Open Science Day and National EOSC Tripartite Event	December 2024	Ljubljana, Slovenia	Presentation of RDA and RDA Europe, presentation of RDA TIGER, engagement of TRUST WG to provide a presentation about trustworthy repositories	National
EUDAT 2024⁸²	December 2024	Karlsruhe, Germany	Presentation of RDA TIGER and the project services with a poster and exhibition booth.	European
Horizon Europe EINSTEIN Project⁸³ Open Science webinar	January 2025	online	Providing general introduction to Open Science and related initiatives at global and European level, including RDA, EOSC, and RDA TIGER. EINSTEIN is a WIDERA European Excellence Initiative project and the presentation supported Open Science capacity building.	European/ Widening Countries

⁸² <https://eosc.eu/events/eudat-conference-2024/>

⁸³ <https://doi.org/10.3030/101136377>

Event	Date	Location	Relevance to RDA TIGER Engagement	Level of engagement
FAIRFest⁸⁴ (Horizon Europe FAIR-IMPACT Project⁸⁵ & FAIRCORE4EOSC final event)	February 2025	The Hague, the Netherlands	Promotion via a poster ⁸⁶ of RDA TIGER outputs around social and technical interoperability as well as TIGER WGs focused on FAIR implementation. Opportunity to showcase how RDA TIGER project and WG outputs align with national FAIR strategies.	INFRA-EOSC projects/International
BRIDGE Conference	March 2025	Bucharest, Romania	Direct engagement with regional stakeholders and national service providers in Eastern Europe as well as with ESFRI/ERIC research infrastructures. Opportunity to encourage participation in TIGER WGs.	European, National
INORMS Conference	May 2025	Madrid, Spain	Engagement of European research managers and policy influencers; discussion of adoption potential of TIGER outputs in institutional frameworks; a poster presentation ⁸⁷ .	European

⁸⁴ <https://eosc.eu/events/fairfest-celebrating-advancements-of-fair-solutions-in-eosc/>

⁸⁵ <https://doi.org/10.3030/101057344>

⁸⁶ Papadopoulou, A., & Lehtsalu, L. (2025). RDA Europe - Facilitating Technical, Semantic & Social Interoperability across borders. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14972554>

⁸⁷ Papadopoulou, A., & Lehtsalu, L. (2025). Seizing Opportunities: The Role of RMAs in the Research Data Alliance (RDA). INORMS Congress 2025, Madrid, Spain. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15495989>

Event	Date	Location	Relevance to RDA TIGER Engagement	Level of engagement
EGI Conference 2025 (RDA TIGER)	June 2025	Santander, Spain	Multiple presentations ^{88 89 90} of TIGER WGs related to infrastructure and interoperability; collaboration with national and pan-European infrastructure providers.	European
LIBER Conference⁹¹	July 2025	Lausanne, Switzerland	Engagement of academic libraries and national networks in the adoption of data stewardship WGs; increased TIGER WG visibility in the Open Science librarian community.	European
Conference on Research Data Infrastructures (CoRDI)⁹²	August 2025	Aachen, Germany	RDA TIGER delivers a poster about facilitation and the importance of such soft infrastructures in the development of effective community based solutions to challenges related to data sharing. The posters are co-developed with Base4NFDI, comparing facilitation services in RDA TIGER and NFDI.	European

⁸⁸ <https://indico.egi.eu/event/6638/contributions/20482/>

⁸⁹ <https://indico.egi.eu/event/6638/contributions/20483/>

⁹⁰ <https://indico.egi.eu/event/6638/contributions/20484/>

⁹¹ <https://liberconference.eu/>

⁹² <https://eosc.eu/events/cordi-2025>

Event	Date	Location	Relevance to RDA TIGER Engagement	Level of engagement
NORFest, Ireland	November 2025	Dublin, Ireland	RDA TIGER engagement with the Irish community led to project members being involved in the programme committee of this initiative of Ireland's National Open Research Forum, funded by the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Science.	National

